

STATE AND LAW

IMPACT OF SAFETY PROCEDURES ON THE PRODUCTION, EMPLOYEES AND ENVIRONMENT AT NOKENG FLUORSPAR MINE FROM 2019-2021

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to evaluate the impact of safety procedures on the production, employees, and environment at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine from 2019 – 2021. The researchers are fully interested in finding ways to implement to maintain a safe working environment. It is essential to have a safe working environment, not only for employees but also for the equipment, which plays a huge part in giving sufficient and quality products. It becomes a major problem, therefore, when safety procedures and measures are not adhered to, a lot is at stake. To aid in the methodical organization of the study, this research report clearly states the problem, the research questions, and its goals. In this study, a research technique is offered to explain how it will be used to successfully accomplish the research objectives. The researcher also wishes to guarantee that the suggested research is conducted ethically and with explanations of its validity. The research results found that bypassing safety procedures has an impact on employees, production, and environment at the mining operation. Production targets were not met, injuries were sustained from employees and environment was polluted. After analysing the results from all the participants, the researcher found that bypassing safety procedures has a negative impact on employees, production, and environment.

Keywords: Safety, Procedures, Production, Employees, Environment, Nokeng Fluorspar Mine.

Introduction

Nokeng Fluorspar Mine is one of the South African mines that mines and processes Fluorspar and it is situated in Northern part of Pretoria. The estimated life span of the mine is 19 years, with an estimated total mineral reserve of 19Mt. At Nokeng an average run-of-time rate of 600 000tpa, production of fluorspar for sale on local and export steel markets is targeted, from surface and open pit mining. In the mining industries safety is a major and sensitive subject; safety simply refers to the “management of operations and events within the mining industry for the protection of miners, environment and equipment, by minimising hazards, risks and accidents” (safeopedia, 2018). Any safety concerns pertaining to mining should be addressed in accordance with applicable laws, regulations, best practices, and procedures. Safety should be taken into serious consideration for the best possible protection of the environment and employees. Management is ultimately responsible for safety; however, the researcher argues that management, employees, labour unions, and the authorities must all share responsibility if safe and healthy workplaces are to be established.

This research aims to evaluate the impact of safety procedures on employees, production, and the environment at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine from 2019 – 2021. The researcher is interested in this subject since she has experienced some challenges and problems with safety procedures at her workplace and this has negatively affected the company, preventing it from performing at

its optimum. To conduct this study, the researcher has drawn up this proposal to explain the intended procedures. A broad introduction, a review of the relevant literature that completely describes and breaks down the research topic, a statement of the research topic, research questions, and objectives are provided in this proposal. The researcher also outlines, in the sections below, the background, rationale, and goals of the study, as well as the ethical issues that will be adhered to.

Research Problem

Background to the problem

Safety is a crucial aspect of the mining industries. Their aim is to practice a “Zero Harm” culture, where they prioritise safety, emphasising that every employee has a right to, daily, return home unharmed. It is also essential to have a safe working environment, not only for employees but also for the equipment, which plays a huge part in giving sufficient and quality products. It becomes a major problem, therefore, when safety procedures and measures are not adhered to, as a lot is at stake. The following problems have been identified at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine (NFM):

a) Safety procedures are not adhered to as people are frequently injured on duty. When this happens, they cannot function as expected - they tend to miss work either due to being admitted to the hospital because of the injury sustained or by staying at home due to the doctor’s orders.

b) Also, unsafe procedures cause a polluted environment around the mine and the nearby places. Unwanted and waste materials from processing in the plant are thrown into the tailing dam. Sometimes the dam overflows onto nearby places and this is a danger to animals and plants. Animals become sick and some even die; similarly, plants are affected.

c) Due to the unsafe condition, the mine is not able to function as effectively as it is supposed to, resulting in poor production.

d) One other problem at NFM, is poor maintenance of equipment. This causes the breakdown of the equipment and sometimes there is a need to totally stop production to fix the equipment.

The impact of non-observance of safety procedures at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine has affected employees, the environment and production, and this is not a good image for the company.

Problem statement

Generally, there has been a poor performance of Nokeng Fluorspar Mine due to safety procedures not being fully implemented on a daily basis. This situation is negatively affecting the organisation, as monthly and daily targets are not being met, and employees are getting sick and injured frequently while on duty. In addition, during production, non-adherence to the safe disposal of waste materials has resulted in the nearby environment being polluted.

- Not paying attention to safety regulations has had a negative effect on production, as daily and monthly targets are not being met; also, unsafe handling of equipment causes continuous breakdowns during operation.

- Poor safety standards have resulted in employees being injured and sick on duty, causing them to stay home to recover as per doctor's instructions and mine regulations which require every employee to be fit to do his/her job.

- While the plant and mine site are operational, some fumes and dust are released, and these pollute the atmosphere. Unwanted materials from the plant are also thrown into the mine's slimes dam and when the dam overflows it spills onto the surrounding areas, where plants grow and animals feed.

Research Questions

Main research question:

- What is the impact of safety procedures on employees, the environment, and production at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine from 2019 – 2021?

- What are the safety procedures that need to be followed to maintain a safe working environment?

- What are the consequences of bypassing safety procedures?

Research Aim and Objectives

Research objectives go into deeper information about the specific study subjects or problems that the project plans to investigate, building on the broad subject covered in the research aim. Typically, at least two or three research goals are stated. These should be numbered so that they may be quickly found in a proposal or report in the future. The main reason the researcher did this study was to gain a thorough grasp of and insight into how the safety measures at Nokeng Fluorspar

Mine might have an adverse effect on the organization's performance.

Research Approach and Methodology

Research Approach

Generally, there has been poor performance from the Nokeng Fluorspar Mine, mainly, because safety procedures for employees, the environment, and during production, are not being adhered to. This situation has negatively impacted the mine, reducing its functionality. In this study a qualitative research method, which is inductive in nature and provides more depth and understanding of a phenomenon, will be used. As indicated interviews will be used; this was deemed an appropriate data collecting instrument as it also allows the researcher to probe and pursue any points/ideas that may emerge during the process. According to (QuestionPro, 2023) qualitative research techniques are made to assist with understanding on how a target audience behaves and thinks about a particular subject. Numerous qualitative research techniques, including in-depth interviews, focus groups, ethnographic studies, content analyses, and case study studies, are frequently employed. Results from qualitative methods are more descriptive, and inferences may be made from the collected data relatively simply.

The researchers applied a qualitative methodology to assess the impact of safety procedures at the Nokeng Fluorspar Mine between 2019 and 2021. Each person has a unique experience, and the researchers took that into account and created interview questions to get insights from specific employees.

Research design/paradigm

Research design

According to QuestionPro, (2022) a research design as a researcher's framework of methodologies and procedures to use in a project. Researchers can make their studies more focused and successful by establishing how they intend to conduct the study right from its inception. In this study, the researcher will evaluate the effects of not stringently following safety procedures at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine. To do so, the researcher intends to use the qualitative approach. This method focuses on the description and narration of feelings, perceptions, and experiences rather than their quantification. It adopts an open, flexible, and unstructured approach to inquiry and attempts to explore diversity rather than quantify it (Kumar, 2019). For data collection, face-to-face interviews will be conducted, by the researcher, with the Nokeng Fluorspar Mine internal divisions that are mainly impacted by safety procedures. "Paradigms can be described as different ways of viewing the world and often form the foundation from which research is undertaken (Davies, 2018). They consist of a set of assumptions about what is reality, how knowledge is created and what is valuable to teach (Davies, 2018). It is important that researchers are clear about their own beliefs and assumptions in this regard" (Davies, 2018). According to (Kivunja, 2017) "the term paradigm is used to describe a researcher's 'worldview'. This worldview is the perspective, or thinking, or school of thought, or set of shared beliefs, that informs the meaning or interpretation of research data". "A research paradigm inherently reflects the

researcher's beliefs about the world that s/he lives in and wants to live in" (Kivunja, 2017). "It constitutes the abstract beliefs and principles that shape how a researcher sees the world, and how s/he interprets and acts within that world" (Kivunja, 2017).

Target group/population

According to Ravikiran, (2023) "Population" is "the whole collection of individuals, items, cases, things, or occurrences of importance under inspection when completing a study". A target ethnic was established prior to the research's conduct, and a sampling frame was selected from that population. Employees from the following Nokeng Fluorspar Mine divisions will make up the study's respondents:

- (a) Five from the processing department,
- (b) Three from the engineering department, and
- (c) Two from the mining environment department.

Sample and sample type

A random sampling method will be used by the researcher, because the anticipated participants are those working around focus, therefore, will provide relevant information. Random sampling indicates that each employee has an equal chance of being chosen as part of the sampling procedure (Bennett, 2022). Meaning "the researcher randomly selects a subset of participants from a population" (Thomas, 2020) and then, data are gathered from as much of this random selection as possible. This indicates that everyone employed by the impacted divisions was eligible to participate in the study.

Data Collection

To accomplish the goals related to their research topics, researchers use methods to collect data (Eng, 2013). A schedule for the interview could help the researchers organised the questions to be asked of participants because making sure that the opinions of the employees within the identified divisions are heard. This process is explained by (Zarinpoush, 2016): "A re-

search interview involves an interviewer, who coordinates the process of the conversation and asks questions, and an interviewee, who responds to those questions". "Interviews are an appropriate method when there is a need to collect in-depth information on people's opinions, thoughts, experiences, and feelings" (Zarinpoush, 2016). In this study all selected study participants will be interviewed to gather data; with each participant, a 15-minute interview will be conducted during their shift for three weeks, at their assigned workstations for the researcher to collect all necessary data. Olson, (2016) explains "An interview is the most common method for gaining information in the social realm, so there are a bewildering array of techniques and strategies for conducting them.... from formal to highly unstructured, individual and group".

Data Analysis

Mihas (2019) described qualitative data as a narrative technique that examines tales as representations of events peculiar to a group of people. The focus of this method of research is on the lived experiences of those who are intimately familiar with the phenomenon and how they experience the phenomenon as it is occurring. Researchers using this approach usually analyse the form and content of the narrative data and in the process isolate themes and sub-themes that emerge. This is the method that will be used to analyse the collected data from the interviews. Leeds, (2023) succinctly states that data is any information that has been gathered, spotted, generated, or developed in order to support primary study conclusions and to enable the reader interpret information correctly.

Findings

Findings are basically what the researchers found during their studies after analysing the collected data. The research findings are facts and phrases, observations, and experimental data resulted from the study. In this study a qualitative data collection method was used and below is the statistics respondent.

Table 1

Statistics of respondents

Code Name	Gender	Age	Years of service
P1	Male	21 - 30	2+
P2	Female	21 - 30	3+
P3	Female	31 - 40	3+
P4	Female	41 - 50	4+
P5	Male	31 - 40	2+
P6	Male	18 - 29	1+
P7	Female	41 - 50	2+
P8	Male	51 - 60	4+
P9	Female	21 - 30	3+
P10	Male	31 - 40	4+

The researcher selected 10 employees to participate in the study. Of the 10 participants, five were females and five males. These participants were drawn from a community of employees from the processing department, engineering department, and mining department. Code names (i.e. P1–P10) were assigned by the researcher for staff members, this is done to maintain anonymity, discretion, and to make it simple to acknowledge speech that was used to generate the data findings. The majority of those involved were qualified

to give knowledge, experience, and expertise about the impact of safety procedures at the Nokeng fluorspar mine.

Participants

Interview questionnaires was conducted through a survey which consisted of six questions, which needed an insight from the randomly selected employees. The survey was completed by ten individuals with equal representation of male and female respondents. As mentioned above these respondents were drawn from

different departments at Nokeng to have unbiased findings. In the findings, all ten participants declared that bypassing safety procedures has negative impact on employees, production, and environment.

Results consistent with the first research objective: -

Safety measures and protocols in the workplace are crucial for protecting employees' physical and emotional well-being. It was identified by participant 1, 5 and 7 that Nokeng employees hardly follow safety procedures such as conducting a SLAM (Stop, Look, Assess and Manage) before commencing with daily tasks. No risk assessments are conducted, proper PPE (Personal Protective Equipment) are not always worn as per company's policy to name a few and all these negatively impact them. From 2019 to 2021 fortunate enough there was not any fatalities, but few employees sustained injuries, many incidents were a near miss, and some were not reported. Participant 2 was one of people working in an area in question, and stated that most employees do not wear PPE such as dust mask in a dusty area, ear plugs in a noisy area, respirators in chemicals areas, there might be health side effects in the long run i.e. respiratory problems, hearing impairment. Whereas participant 9 and 10 showed that there are those employees who occasionally followed safety procedures and only when it was suitable for them. For instance, it is required that employees conduct an inspection in their area of work, daily. But most employees conduct inspection when they feel they want to or when their superiors are looking for inspection lists. This makes accidents or breakdown that could have been prevented to occur.

The impact of safety on environment was also identified. Participant six and three explained that during the processing of fluorspar dust is generated when crushing the material, fumes are also generated during steam production and such causes air pollution. Furthermore, an environment is impacted by chemicals spillages and leaking pumps in the plant. Chemicals spill mostly during their preparation time. Chemicals such as soda ash, collector, and dextrin are used during the production of fluorspar, and these spills causes harm to the nearby environment as they flow into the water used in the plant for processing and water going to tailings dam. They also mentioned that leaking pumps causes slurry to flow out of the bund wall if not fully controlled through good housekeeping in the bund wall and thus creating a slippery walking area on the nearby environment. Lastly but not least the impact of safety on production was identified. Participant number 4 and 8 stated that poor maintenance to the equipment used in the plant resulted into poor quality product produced. A targeted 97% grade of Acid Fluorspar should be produced but as a result a lower grade is sometimes produced. It was also stated that there were many plant breakdowns occurring in a month, resulting to high downtime, and not meeting the monthly target of 15000 tons of Acid Fluorspar grade. Poor maintenance causes poor performance, causing company not to be more effective.

Results in accordance with the second research objective.

In a mine, bypassing safety protocols can have negative impacts on both the operation of the mine as a whole and the lives of those involved. Below are some of the consequences of bypassing safety procedures that were identified by the ten participants involved in this study.

- Increased risk of accidents occurrence: - Safety procedures are intended to reduce hazards and stop workplace accidents. The likelihood of accidents happening is greatly increased by ignoring these measures. For the workers, this may result in accidents, fatalities, and long-term health problems.

- Loss of lives: - Bypassing safety precautions may result in major accidents or disasters that cause the death of people. For the impacted families and co-workers', the physical and emotional repercussions are immense.

- Damage to equipment: - Bypassing these protocols may result in equipment damage, breakdowns, or malfunctions. This not only has an impact on the business's operational effectiveness, but also raises the danger of accidents and production delays.

- Environmental impact: - Bypassing these protocols may lead to the release of hazardous substances or the inappropriate disposal of waste, both of which can cause environmental damage. Ecological harm, regulatory non-compliance, and reputational harm can result from this.

- Legal penalties: - Legal repercussions for the mine management and those in charge of safety monitoring may occur from disregarding safety procedures. For breaking safety rules, authorities may punish, penalize, or take legal action against the mine. This could harm the mine's reputation and create financial obligations.

Keep in mind that increasing mine safety is a continuous process that calls for dedication from all levels of the company. The dangers connected with mining operations can be greatly decreased by putting these strategies into practice and encouraging a safety-conscious culture.

Importance of safety in the mines according to MHSA (Mine Health and Safety Act)

After apartheid was abolished in the late 1980s and a constitutional democracy was established in 1994, South Africa implemented a corpus of mining legislation, which includes, the Mine Health and Safety Act (MHSA) of 1996. The Mine Health and Safety Act mainly governs health and safety in the mining industry in South Africa (Council, 2018). The importance of safety in mines, according to the Mine Health and Safety Act (MHSA), is paramount to protect the lives and well-being of mine workers. The MHSA is a legislative framework that sets out guidelines and regulations for promoting health and safety in mining operations (Council, 2018). Here are some key reasons why safety is crucial in mines, as emphasized by the MHSA: Preservation of Human Life: The primary focus of mine safety is to prevent accidents, injuries, and fatalities. Mining operations involve various hazards such as cave-ins, explosions, toxic gases, chemicals, dust, and

machinery accidents. Adhering to safety standards helps minimize these risks and ensures the preservation of human life.

Protection of employees Health: Mines often expose workers to harmful substances such as dust, silica, asbestos, and various chemicals. Prolonged exposure to these substances can lead to serious respiratory diseases, lung disorders, and other health issues. Safety measures outlined in the MHSA aim to protect miners from these occupational hazards.

Prevention of Accidents and Incidents: By implementing safety protocols and procedures, mines can minimize the occurrence of accidents and incidents. This includes conducting risk assessments, providing appropriate training and supervision, using proper protective equipment, and maintaining safe working conditions. Prevention is vital to reduce injuries, property damage, and environmental harm.

Legal Compliance: Compliance with the MHSA is not only crucial for the well-being of mine workers but also a legal requirement. The MHSA sets standards and regulations that mining companies must follow to ensure safe working conditions. Failure to comply with these regulations can lead to legal consequences, including fines, penalties, and potential closure of the mine.

Improved Productivity and Efficiency: A safe work environment promotes higher productivity and efficiency. When workers feel safe and protected, they can focus on their tasks without constant fear or distraction. Additionally, safety measures can help prevent equipment breakdowns, production delays, and disruptions, leading to smoother operations and improved productivity.

Reputation and Community Relations: Safety practices in mines influence the reputation and community relations of mining companies. Demonstrating a commitment to safety fosters trust among stakeholders, including employees, local communities, regulatory bodies, and investors. It enhances the company's image as a responsible and ethical organization. Overall, the main objective of MHSA is to safeguard the lives and well-being of workers, prevent accidents, protect worker's health, ensure legal compliance, improve productivity, and maintain positive community relations in the mine (Council, 2018). There are many Acts that govern the mining industry but there are few that stand out and are considered the main ones; below is a discussion of them.

- **Section 22 of Mine Health and Safety Act**

It addresses “employees’ duties for health and safety”.

It outlines that all employees at the mine must:

(a) “Take reasonable care to protect their health and safety”; (Council, Mine Health and Safety Act No.29 of 1996 and Regulations, 2018)

(b) “Take reasonable care to protect the health and safety of other persons who may be affected by any act or omission of that employee”; (Council, Mine Health and Safety Act No.29 of 1996 and Regulations, 2018)

© “Use and take proper care of protective clothing, and other health and safety facilities and equipment

provided for the protection, health or safety of that employee and other employees”; (Council, Mine Health and Safety Act No.29 of 1996 and Regulations, 2018)

- **Section 23 of Mine Health and Safety**

It states the “employees’ rights to leave a dangerous working place” (Council, Mine Health and Safety Act No.29 of 1996 and Regulations, 2018). Employees are allowed to leave any workplace whenever, if:

(a) At such workplace, events occur that, with reasonable justification, in their opinion, present a significant threat to the worker's wellbeing or safety; or

(b) The worker is instructed to leave the workplace by the health and safety person in charge of that location.

(c) Notification of supervisors and health and safety representatives of dangers that have been perceived and addressed.

- **Section 83 of Mine Health and Safety Act**

It states that “No discrimination against employees who exercises rights” (Council, Mine Health and Safety Act No 29 of 1996 and Regulations, 2018).

This Act outlines that:

(a) No one is allowed to treat an employee unfairly because of exercising a right under this Act or a collective agreement that is being considered by this Act;

(b) Engaging in any activity to which the employee is entitled under this Act or a collective agreement envisioned by this Act;

(c) Refusing to carry out any action that the employee is forbidden from carrying out under the conditions of this Act or a collective agreement that is covered by this Act.

The Department of Mineral Resources does site visits of the mines, in order to check and ensure that such Acts as mentioned above are followed and in place at all times. If not, measures are taken against the mining institution for not practicing safety procedures.

Safety Procedures in the Workplace

According to Indeed, (2022) a procedure “is a method for completing something with steps and instructions for each aspect of the task”. Certain safety procedures are used daily, monthly, or yearly to accomplish a safe working environment in the mines. Below are the procedures for ensuring safety:

- When every Mining institution hires new employees, it is a requirement for the latter to undergo a medical examination before entering any working sites; this is done to make sure the employee is fit for the job.

- Induction is then a follow-up step, which can take a day to a month depending on institutions. It is conducted to familiarise a new employee with the new working environment, its rules, regulations, and procedures. Both induction and medical assessment are renewed on a yearly basis.

- Employees are required to wear a full PPE (Personal Protective Equipment) when entering the workplace. These differ according to the site, but a full work suit, safety boots, reflective vest, helmet, safety goggles, and hearing protection should always be worn. All these are provided by the company.

- At the start of every new shift, a safety meeting is conducted by all members of the ongoing shift, a safety topic is read and discussed, and all members

have to sign and acknowledge their understanding of the topic or any new development. This is done daily.

- The new shift is then allowed to enter the working site. Before commencing with daily tasks, the on-shift has to handover to the oncoming shift. This is where everything that happened during the previous shift is discussed; new instructions, completed tasks, and any outstanding jobs are all discussed.

- The new shift can now take over, but firstly pre-inspections should be conducted, and all these have their paperwork. A risk assessment is then written by all members of the section; this is done to identify hazards and risks, introduce controls, and eliminate anything that poses a threat. All members must discuss, then sign.

- Now the new team is ready to start working. During operations, if there are any hazards identified, it is a requirement that they are written down, discussed, and controls introduced. Housekeeping is also conducted during the operations, to keep the working place clean and safe.

- If there is any breakdown, a job request is written down by CRO (Control Room Operator) to the engineering team to attend to the matter. Some breakdowns require a stoppage to attend to the matter. Maintenance is also done on equipment on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis.

- For the engineering team to work, permits are required from the foreman and supervisors, this is to ensure that the work is conducted, safely.

Impact of safety procedures on Employees

Safety procedures are critical for ensuring the well-being of employees who work in mines. It is important for employees to know what is required and expected of them from the institution they work for. Employees may take shortcuts while operating equipment, have bad behaviour and attitude towards their work. Some use “I have been here for long” attitude and bypass the stipulated steps; all these pose a threat to their health and safety. Some careless employees end up sustaining serious injuries or causing damage to or failure of equipment because they do not follow correct safety procedures.

Accidents and incidents prevention is of essence in the mining industry. To maintain these annual trainings and refreshers are attended by each employee, training such as “Lock –Out, Over-head crane operation, Confined space and the like are conducted to maintain a safe working environment. It is compulsory for every employee to attend these trainings and inductions, to have a clearly defined working procedures. Furthermore, the impact of safety procedures on employees at mines is significant, both in terms of their physical safety and their mental health. In terms of physical safety, safety procedures can help to prevent accidents and injuries that may otherwise occur in a hazardous work environment. These procedures may include things like wearing personal protective equipment, following specific work procedures, and receiving regular safety training such as “HIRA – Hazard

Identification and Risk Assessment” training. By following these procedures, employees can reduce their risk of injury or illness. In addition, safety procedures can also have an impact on employees' mental health. Working in a mine can be a stressful and dangerous job, and strict safety procedures can help to alleviate some of that stress by providing a sense of security and predictability. When employees feel that their employer is taking their safety seriously, they are more likely to feel valued and supported in their work.

Impact of safety procedures on Production

Production is the main function of the mining industries which can be impacted in many ways if safety procedures are not followed. When correct safety procedures are bypassed a lot is at stake, here are some of the effects on production,

- Reduced accidents and injuries: Implementing diligent safety procedures helps prevent accidents and injuries among mine workers. This leads to fewer disruptions in operations caused by incidents, which can result in lost work hours, production delays, and increased costs associated with medical treatment and compensation (Maly, n.d.).

- Improved employee morale and retention: A safe working environment fosters positive employee morale and job satisfaction. When workers feel secure and protected, they are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and productive.

- Compliance with regulations and legal requirements: Adhering to mines regulations is crucial for avoiding penalties, fines, and legal liabilities. By implementing effective safety procedures, mines ensure compliance with the law, minimizing the risk of legal issues that could disrupt production and negatively impact the mine's reputation. For example, a non-compliant mine can get a section 54 act of MHSA, which command mine closure and stoppage with immediate effect (M. Mpanza, n.d.).

- Optimal use of resources: Safety procedures often involve risk assessments, hazard identification, and the development of protocols to mitigate potential dangers. By proactively addressing safety risks, mines can optimize the use of resources, such as equipment, machinery, and personnel. For example, regular equipment maintenance and inspections can prevent breakdowns and unplanned downtime, ensuring smooth production processes (Maly, n.d.).

- Enhanced operational efficiency: Annual trainings programs contribute to improved operational efficiency, as they establish clear guidelines and promote consistent practices among workers. By minimizing errors, rework, communication breakdowns, and enhance overall productivity.

All these are threats to well-functioning and more productive environment; the outcome is that the company operates at a loss. A picture below shows a monthly total production with all breakdowns that took place during the month. A monthly production target is 15000 tons of Acid grade fluorspar and only 12000 tons were produced in the month of April 2023 as shown below.

Figure: 1 NFM production Acid Spar April 2023

Impact of Safety on the environment

According to Programme, (2022) an environment is “a sum total of all the living and non-living elements and their effects that influence human life. While all living or biotic elements are animals, plants, forests, fisheries, and birds, non-living or abiotic elements include water, land, sunlight, rocks, and air”. It is very essential to keep the mining environment safe and clean. Mining operations can have significant environmental impacts, including land degradation, soil erosion, water pollution, and air pollution (LexisNexis, 2022). Safety procedures can help to mitigate these impacts by minimizing the amount of waste generated, reducing the risk of spills and leaks, and controlling the release of pollutants. For instance during production, the unwanted materials in the form of water or slurry are thrown into a mining dam, and this dam has to be maintained so that it does not overflow onto the ground and cause harm to living and non-living things. Dust and fumes are also generated during operations, but they should be controlled so that they do not cause pollution. The Environmental safety team must maintain a healthy environment, if not DMR could revoke the mine’s license, thereby stopping any further operations (M. Mpanza, n.d.).

Limitations

David Phair, (2022) shows that at their most basic level, research limitations are the shortcomings of the study that are frequently due to circumstances outside your control as the researcher. These variables might include things like time, financial accessibility, equipment, data, or participants. Nokeng Fluorspar Mine is a middle-sized company which uses both day-to-day normal shift and 6 to 6 shift work. When other shift is off duty, others are on duty. This made data collection a bit difficult as process, engineering and mining department work different shifts, and more time was required to fully collect data. This limited the variance of response and delayed the gathering of data.

Conclusion

During this study it was seen from the literature review that safety is a major concern in the mining industry. Though it is a significant thing, it is not fully practised daily, and this has a negative impact on employees, production and the operational environment. The impact of safety procedures on employees, production, and environment at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine was fully discussed. The researchers found that safety procedures are not fully implemented. As a results production targets are not always met, poor equipment maintenance also causes increase in downtime and delays during production. On the other hand, employees are also getting injured on duty due to bypassing some of the

safety procedures, there are lots of near miss and some employees fall sick by not adhering to safety protocols. Finally, the environment in which they operate in, is also affected. Chemical spills and leaks contaminate the environment. During production dust and fumes are also generated which causes air pollution to the nearby environment. To deal with all these, there were controls that were identified and put in place to have a safe working environment from now going forth. So, it can be concluded that bypassing safety procedures have an impact on employees, production, and environment.

International/National and Managerial Implications

International Implications:

1. **Compliance with International Standards:** The impact of safety procedures at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine has implications on the mine's compliance with international safety standards such as those set by the International Labour Organization (ILO) and International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM). Adherence to these standards ensures that the mine operates in a responsible and sustainable manner, maintaining the confidence of international stakeholders.

2. **Reputation and Market Access:** The safety record and environmental performance of Nokeng Fluorspar Mine can have an impact on its reputation and market access. International buyers, investors, and partners may consider the mine's safety practices and environmental impact when making decisions regarding business relationships and supply chain sustainability.

National Implications:

1. **Legal Compliance:** Safety procedures at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine must align with national mining regulations and occupational health and safety (OHS) laws. Compliance with these regulations ensures the mine operates legally and avoids penalties or sanctions imposed by national authorities.

2. **Economic Contribution:** The impact of safety procedures on production can have economic implications at the national level. A safe working environment reduces accidents, injuries, and associated costs, resulting in increased productivity, reduced downtime, and improved financial performance. This, in turn, contributes positively to the mine's profitability and potential economic benefits for the local community and the national economy.

Managerial Implications:

1. **Employee Morale and Productivity:** Safety procedures have a direct impact on employee morale and productivity at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine. Implementing robust safety measures creates a sense of security and well-being among employees, leading to higher job satisfaction, improved motivation, and increased productivity levels.

2. **Cost Management:** Effective safety procedures can help manage costs associated with accidents, injuries, and operational disruptions. By minimizing incidents and their subsequent financial implications (e.g., medical expenses, legal fees, and equipment damage), the mine can optimize its financial resources and allocate them to other areas of importance.

3. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Safety procedures and their impact on the environment can influence

stakeholder perception and engagement. Engaging with local communities, environmental groups, and other stakeholders through transparent communication about safety measures and environmental initiatives fosters trust, collaboration, and long-term relationships.

4. **Regulatory Compliance:** Managers at Nokeng Fluorspar Mine must ensure that safety procedures are compliant with regulatory requirements. It is their responsibility to stay updated on relevant regulations, implement necessary changes to meet evolving standards, and maintain a proactive approach towards safety and environmental management.

5. **Continuous Improvement:** The impact of safety procedures should drive a culture of continuous improvement within the organization. Managers should encourage feedback from employees, conduct regular safety audits, and invest in training and technology to enhance safety practices and minimize risks.

By considering these international, national, and managerial implications, Nokeng Fluorspar Mine can proactively address safety, employee well-being, and environmental concerns while ensuring compliance and sustainable operations.

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